

National and International Environmental Law and Justice

The Unresolved Issues

5. Green Crimes-Eco-Global Criminology-Green Criminology

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Within the same discourse about the unresolved issues in environmental law and justice, environmental/ecological crimes, both at national and international/global levels remain an aspect of crimes against the natural environment that existing laws fail to curtail, or even address through appropriate international criminological platforms, or through existing judicial prescriptions. Apart from decades of discussions and data collecting on environmental/ecological crimes and efforts for control and redress, it has also become both necessary and important to analyze recent propositions of embedding within existing legal frameworks the concept of Eco-Global Criminology, Green Crimes and the concept of Green Criminology, which also include Corporate Environmental Crimes, Trans National Environmental Crimes, White Collar Environmental Crimes, Eco/Environmental Terrorism, and the crime of Ecocide, all of which have been around for too long with little efforts for either curtailment, or punishment, or redress. However, it needs to be emphasized that all forms and instances of environmental/ecological crimes should be in the first instance analysed and discussed to understand and appreciate their causes and implications. The new concept of green criminology and how it may be better adapted to resolve both national and global environmental/ecological crimes and criminal activities through legal precepts has been foregrounded in numerous discussions over the past decades, and need particular consideration for revival.

Humans have been committing crimes against both the human and natural environments in various forms and intensities since the beginning of times. Accentuated since the industrial revolution, such crimes have always been left to the national or domestic legislatures for redressment or punishment. Through the 1980s and beyond, the public, mostly concerned with the environment they live in, or the human environment, usually have linked environmental crimes leading to environmental degradation with human actions and activities within the precincts of the human environment. As such, environmental crime has been defined as crime against the environment in terms of disregard, or in contravention to existing environmental legislations, and stands liable to prosecution in an appropriate court of law. Some examples of such crimes, but far from being exhaustive, include:

- Contaminating water by dumping chemicals into a stream or river;
- Releasing pollutants into the air; on land and into watercourses;
- Improper disposal, storage, or transportation of hazardous wastes;
- Trade in endangered species (fauna and flora); and
- Destruction of forests, watercourses, water bodies and habitats through commercial activities

Since these earlier efforts, criminologists have significantly expanded the list of what should be classified as environmental crimes, and South and Beirne (1998) encourage further exploration of the following types of crimes:

1. The abuse and exploitation of ecological systems, including nonhuman animals;
2. Corporate disregard for damage to land or air or water quality;
3. Profiteering from environmentally damaging trades and practices that destroy lives and leave a legacy of damage for subsequent generations;
4. Military actions in war that adversely affect the environment and wildlife;
5. New challenges to international treaties and to the emerging field of bio-ethics, such as bio-piracy;
6. Illicit markets in nuclear materials; and
7. Legal monopolization of natural resources (for example, privatization, patenting of natural products) leading to divisions between the resource-rich and the resource-impooverished countries, and the prospects of new forms of conflict, harm, injury, damage, and crime.

Discussing the shortcomings of the broader justice perspectives of defining environmental/ecological crimes, Lynch and Stretesky (2003) propose three elements crucial in identifying environmental criminology with an ecocentric rather than an anthropocentric bias:

1. An act that may or may not violate existing rules and environmental regulations;
2. Acts that have identifiable environmental damage outcomes; and
3. Acts that originate from human action.

Discouraging on the ambiguities of environmental crime, Halsey (2004) and Hauck (2008) propound that '*strict legalist and socio-legal definitions of environmental crime*' may have failed to recognize that the current regulatory system is anthropocentric (human-centred), often to the detriment of natural systems, assuming that environmental harms result from a failure of the existing legal system and may only be addressed by modifying the system. As such, environmental harms that are not addressed by regulatory agencies are ignored. In addition, and similar to the observations of Beirne and South (2007) and White (2011), these perspectives ignore the dimensions of power in the construction of the law. Halsey (2004) and Hauck (2008) further argue that:

The formation of law and the power dynamics influencing such processes are critical aspects that need to be acknowledged and understood.

According to the Environmental Investigation Agency (EIA, 2008), International Environmental Crime can be defined across five broad areas of offences which have been recognised by bodies such as the G8, Interpol, the EU, the UN Environment programme and the UN Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute, including:

1. Illegal trade in wildlife in contravention to the 1973 Washington Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Fauna and Flora (CITES);
2. Illegal trade in ozone-depleting substances (ODS) in contravention to the 1987 Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer;
3. Dumping and illegal transport of various kinds of hazardous waste in contravention of the 1989 Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movement of Hazardous Wastes and other Wastes and their Disposal;
4. Illegal, unregulated and unreported (IUU) fishing in contravention to controls imposed by various regional fisheries management organisations (RMFOs); and

5. Illegal logging and trade in timber when timber is harvested, transported, bought or sold in violation of national laws There are currently no binding international controls on the international timber trade with the exception of endangered species, which is covered by CITES).

It is to be noted that these are the *'identifiable'* crimes and several international conventions dwell on the illegality of certain actions detrimental to the natural environment, but there are hardly any specific mention of appropriate international laws that deal with such actions. The root causes of environmental crime vary greatly and subsequently the design, identification, and implementation of appropriate responses must be carefully planned. Root causes are primarily the low risks and high profits in a permissive environment as a result of poor governance and widespread corruption, minimal budgets to police, prosecution and courts, inadequate institutional support, political interference and low employee morale, minimal benefits to local communities and rising demands, claims the EIA. Also, the availability of markets and poverty should be of concern. Hence, organized crime has found a virtual free haven to operate.

After decades of efforts against drugs, prostitution and human trafficking, with laws, customs, police and prosecution efforts, these traditional crime areas are perceived as higher risk, though still thriving. At the opposite scale are environmental crimes, which offer a low risk permissive environment, where items such as timber, fish, wildlife, waste, carbon, gold and minerals can be transported freely and traded with a few bribes or even rudimentary falsified or purchased *'permits,'* reports the EIA (2008).

As a result of weak environmental legislation and continued adverse public opinion regarding the management of the environment, several governments have established various environmental enforcement regimes that dramatically increase the legal powers of environmental investigators. The inclusion of criminal sanctions, significant increases in fines coupled with possible imprisonment of offenders can change the face of environmental law enforcement. Enforcing environmental laws and regulations is an important ingredient in protecting the environment and reducing environmental harm. This is generally achieved by various environmental law enforcement agencies operating at an International, Regional, National, State and Local level.

Environmental law enforcement agencies and police services do not operate in a vacuum; the legislative instruments that political systems implement govern their activities and responsibilities within society. However, it is the legislative instruments implemented by governments that determine many of the strategies utilised by police services in protecting the environment. Generally, these International, Regional, National and State legislative instruments are designed to ensure that industries, individuals, and even governments comply with the various environmental obligations embedded in international, regional or national statutes and laws. There are also international legal instruments and treaties that affect the way that sovereign states deal with environmental issues. But these appear to be either not enough or not adequately formulated to deal with green crimes.

In the field of the international protection of human rights, international and regional treaties allow individuals rights of petition to international institutions. Human rights conventions also require regular reports from member states of their record of implementation and state representatives are regularly questioned on these. The legal mechanisms of international human rights law afford far greater protection than that of international environmental law.

A truly effective international environmental legal system will need to be modelled on similar types of institutional and legal frameworks. In other words, the human rights law should be a possible model for international environmental criminal law that deals with harms or threatened harms that significantly affect the global ecological balance.

Remarking that human rights law is only concerned with the protection of the individual, whereas environmental law is concerned with the protection of nature for the ultimate benefit of mankind, Kris and Shelton (1991) observe that human rights activists consistently refuse to acknowledge the obvious connection between human rights and environmental protection. That attitude has not changed and is mainly due to the concern that a new environmental human right would devalue the previously recognized human rights. Discussing these persisting issues, Hodkova (1991) concludes that:

The overlap of interests provides the basis for a limited merger of human rights law and environmental law to create a '*human right to a healthy environment*'. The link between the environmental and human right is increasingly being recognized by legal scholars.

However, it needs to be noted the UN Human Rights Council (UN-UHCR, 2021) has adopted a resolution recognizing that '*the right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment is a human right.*' However, merely recognising such a right without the force any legal framework to legally enforce that right remains purely an intelligent statement.

Contemporary traditional environmental criminologists, mainly concerned with the anthropocentric perspective of environmental crimes, that is crimes that have a negative end-effects on human beings, have concentrated on enacting numerous appropriate legal instruments for prosecutions, punishments, or redressment, and innumerable municipal and government by-Laws exist to ensure punishment/redress of crimes that primarily affect the human environment adversely. However, ecocentric crimes against the environment on a different dimension have been going on without the protection of appropriate laws. Additionally, what is even of more serious concern is that such ecocentric crimes have been tolerated and allowed to take an international dimension with serious global environmental, human rights and financial repercussions today.

According to Cho (2000), an environmental/ecological criminal law legally binding the citizens of all nations does not exist, nor is there an organization to which such a legislative competence could be granted. The result is that presently the prosecution of environmental/ecological crimes, which international environmental conventions have introduced, is only possible before national courts. Additionally, remarks Cho, the shortcomings still remains that:

1. National law does not reach the conduct of international operators,
2. It is not governed by any relevant international regime, and
3. It cannot operate free of either private or any existing public regulatory constraints, or both.

Cho (2000) further observes that the development of international environmental law is subject to the basic handicap that existing environmental law functions at most within the interstate systems. As such it is difficult for a system based on inter-state relations to regulate international impacts and effects. In other words, there is no international super legislature to establish international environmental/ecological criminal laws and no effective international mechanism with enforcement authority, simply because the necessary efforts have not yet been made.

Accordingly to White (2008), humans are the main cause of environmental/ecological harm and need to be controlled through criminalizing additional human activities through appropriate legal instruments. Consequently, White proposes two distinct typologies of environmental/ecological crime that would prioritize the intrinsic value of ecosystems over human interests:

1. Primary: direct destruction and degradation of environmental resources, and
2. Secondary: violations of rules that regulate environmental disasters and environmental crime.

Since its inception in 1984, the Environmental Investigation Agency (EIA) has been exposing environmental crime around the globe and has been seeking greater political support for strong enforcement against these crimes, but in vain. Yet despite the fact that environmental crime poses a growing threat, and such threats have engaged environmental criminologists around the world to raise the alarm with facts and suggestions, it remains a low priority for the international enforcement community and international judiciary systems. Perceived erroneously as '*victimless*' and low on the priority list, such crimes often fail to prompt the required response from global platforms and the global enforcement community. In reality, the impacts affect all of society globally, whether directly or indirectly.

In a (2008) report, the EIA stresses once again on the urgency of effective environmental laws by stating:

The development of statutory enforcement agencies has struggled to keep pace with such change, and issues such as jurisdictions restricting efforts to foster better cross-border cooperation against crimes like illegal logging. These factors lead to a situation where environmental crimes offer high profits and minimal risk. It is time for the international community to wake-up to the menace of environmental crime and show the necessary political will to tackle the criminal gangs plundering our planet for a quick profit.

In spite of numerous reports from the EIA and other organisations, the United Nation's Resolution against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC, 2003) does not explicitly define '*organized crime*' in connection with international environmental crimes, but rather limits it to four offences:

1. Corruption (Article 8),
2. Money-laundering (Article 6),
3. Obstruction of justice (Article 23), and
4. Participation in an organized criminal group (Article 5).

UNTOC's approach appears to be purely academic rather than practical. Although UNTOC recognises the necessity of a wider approach to international criminal activities, it '*intentionally*' fails to define transnational organized crime or list the kinds of crimes that might constitute it, simply to enable a broader applicability of the convention on new and emerging forms of crime.

The United Nations' International Law Commission's Draft Articles on State Responsibility (2001) is generally endorsed by the international community, although state criminal responsibility remains controversial, and at the most elusive. However, that does not diminish the force of the following statement in the commentary to article 19 of the ILC:

The astounding progress of modern science, although it has produced and continues to produce marvellous achievements of great benefit to mankind, nevertheless imparts a capacity to inflict kinds of damage which would be fearfully destructive not only of man's potential for

economic and social development but also of his health and of the very possibility of survival for the present and future generations.

Article 19 of the ILC delivers an all-meaning statement from the UN, but the organisation does not appear to have any plans to follow up with solutions. The one question that has often been asked is, apart from making sensible and meaningful statements, why do not the UN step up efforts to come up with international legal instruments that would change an unacceptable situation?

In yet another academic statement, the United Nations (UN, 2004) recognises that there are many drivers of environmental crimes, most notably economic benefits, substantial demand, and institutional and regulatory failures that results in impunity, and further establishing that the influence of such drivers might slightly differ depending on the type of environmental crimes. The World Bank Institute (WBI, 2000) also recognises that negative impacts of environmental crimes would undermine sustainable development and contribute to the acceleration of climate change, mainly through accelerated tropical deforestation. Limiting environmental crimes to just two issues hardly raise confidence in the WBI. The UN (2004) further establishes that such crimes undermine the rule of law, good governance, and fuel geopolitical conflicts, and in many cases, deprive governments of vast revenues that could have been used to support development, legitimate businesses and markets.

Over a decade later, the United Nations (UNEP, 2018) expands its outlook in recognising that environmental crimes are some of the most profitable forms of transnational criminal activity, the monetary value of these crimes estimated at between USD 91-259 billion annually, and most likely the fourth largest criminal area in the world after drugs, counterfeits and human trafficking. The estimate corresponds to a 26% increase compared to the previous estimate in 2014, with the annual rates of such crimes expected to further increase by 5-7%, as per the projections of Nellemann et al. (2016). According to the United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute (UN-UNICRI, 2018), environmental crimes can be perpetrated by a range of actors, from individuals, small groups, companies and corporations, corrupt government individuals, organised criminal networks, and often a combination of all these. In spite of so much information and data gathered about the ever-increasing incidence of environmental crimes, yet so little effort made to stop the scourge.

However, the UN reports only establish the severity of the problem, but hardly discuss the cause, or the solution. There have been numerous reports about environmental/ecological crimes committed by businesses, especially corporations, and the terms '*Environmental Crime*,' '*Ecological Crime*,' '*Green Crime*,' '*White Collar Crime*,' '*Eco-Global Crime*' '*Ecocide*' and others have been widely used and discussed, and the involvement of corporations, whether national or transnational, exposed.

Over some four decades ago, Michalowski and Kramer (1987) warned that for over two decades transnational corporations (TNCs) have significantly expanded their operations in developing countries, mainly in the South, where legal controls over injurious corporate activities have not grown commensurately, and about which the UN does not appear to be concerned. As a result, TNCs operating in developing host nations have engaged legally in a variety of injurious actions that would have been violations of criminal, regulatory, or civil law in their home countries.

Michalowski and Kramer (1987) conclude that:

The differences in the laws of home and host nations, and the ability of TNCs to influence the legal climate in host countries, renders the laws derived at the level of nation-states an unsatisfactory basis for determining the scope of criminological research on TNCs.

In the early days of environmental legislation, violations carried largely insignificant civil fines and penalties. Initial environmental laws and regulations had little or no deterrent effect on corporations, organised individual groups, or governments, to comply with environmental laws. When sanction is limited to fines, many corporations would take it in their stride as a cost of doing business. The typical example is that in many instances, corporations would find it more cost-effective to continue to pollute more than the law allows and simply pay any associated fines, if indeed the corporation concerned was actually found and convicted of violating environmental laws or regulations. Perversely, corporations may actually find it a disincentive to comply with environmental laws or regulations if compliance would generally raised their operational costs, which means that many corporations obeying the environmental laws, whether out of a sense of legal duty or public obligation, may find themselves disadvantaged and lose a competitive edge and consequently suffer in the marketplace to competitors willing to disregard environmental laws and regulations, conclude Michalowski and Kramer (1987).

Attempts within the United Nations to redefine the meaning of corporate crime by creating agreements, protocols and codes of conduct for international businesses, and continuous efforts on the other hand by U.S. business interests to limit these have been a subject of debate over what constitutes corporate transgressions. Michalowski and Kramer (1987) argue that:

Utilizing the concept of critical reflexivity, the study of corporate transgression by TNCs can legitimately embrace not only violations of law, but also violations of international agreements and codes, and in many cases even violation of human rights.

In May 2002, the Royal Institute of International Affairs (RIIA/Chatham House, 2002) convened a workshop in London on environmental black markets, yet another facet of environmental crime. The workshop's conclusions compiled in *'International Environmental Crime: The Nature and Control of Environmental Black Markets'*, emphasize that illegal trade can be curbed if:

1. Countries are willing to target flagrant violators,
2. There are substantial increases in the use of sanctions and other penalties,
3. Compliance through positive incentives are encourage, and
4. Enforcement agencies are mandated to use identifying documents to flag MEA-governed shipments.

Stakeholders of the RIIA have also suggested that countries must improve law enforcement coordination and information gathering, preferably through some sort of independent international body. Along these lines, UNEP subsequently announced the creation of its *'GreenCustoms'* programme, launched in June 2003, with the aim to improve coordinated intelligence gathering and training of customs agents empowered to monitor MEA-designated shipments and distinguish them from the overwhelming volume of international cargo. Again what is found lacking in the programme are the legal instruments necessary for legal investigations and action at an international level, hence the ineffectiveness of the programme.

In 2015, the United Nations General Assembly declared the illicit trade in flora and fauna a form of serious transnational organised crime (CITES, 2015), leaving CITES to include the legal aspects of the crime into its mandate. Yet CITES continue to assign the responsibility to countries affected by such crimes, with the knowledge that sovereign states only have jurisdiction on their own national criminals, but not on international environmental criminals, and organised international criminal organisations that may comprise of several nations.

Many international conventions require states that are parties to the convention to develop appropriate national domestic legislation to punish prohibited acts. The first type requires the contracting parties to take *'appropriate measures to ensure the application of the agreement in question and the punishment of infractions against those provisions.'* These types of provisions are found in some fifteen multilateral agreements relating to the environment. They are also found in a number of bilateral and multilateral instruments. Some agreements expressly recognize their deterrent function to the effect that *'the penalties specified under the law of a party shall be adequate in severity to discourage violations of the present convention.'* Strictly speaking, conventions are generally only a source of obligation, not a source of law, or for law enforcement, and neither do they have any clout on international criminals.

Interpol, an organization facilitating international police cooperation, began fighting environmental crime in 1992, and remarks that criminals exploit the lack of international consensus and the divergence of approaches taken by countries. What may constitute a crime in one country, may not in another. This effectively enables criminals to go *'forum shopping'* and use for example *'one country to conduct a crime, another to prepare merchandise, and export via a third transit country,'* as elaborated upon in a UNEP-INTERPOL Report (2016). The Report concludes that:

Identifying the optimal legal framework for preventing, combating and prosecuting environmental crimes requires careful consideration.

In April 2016 the first IUCN World Environmental Law Congress convened in Rio de Janeiro. The event was part of a series designed to strengthen the work of judiciaries in implementing the rule of environmental law. The participants in Rio offered a definition of *'environmental rule of law'* as:

The application of the rule of law at local, national, regional and international levels in the environmental context.

But participants appear to have been reluctant to define environmental/ecological crime prior to discussing the rule of law, hence working on the issue from the tailend rather than the head. They further declared that:

1. Strengthening the rule of law in the environmental arena is critical to the achievement of environmental sustainability and sustainable development.
2. Without the rule of law and enforcement of legal rights and obligations, environmental governance, conservation and protection may be arbitrary, subjective and unpredictable.

The Chief Justices, Heads of Jurisdictions, Attorneys General, Auditors General, Chief Prosecutors and other high-ranking representatives gathering in Rio agreed on a list of seven core principles to strengthen the environmental rule of law, including:

1. Fair, clear and implementable environmental laws;
2. Public participation in decision-making, and access to justice and information

- In environmental matters, in accordance with Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration;
3. Accountability and integrity of institutions and decision-makers, including through the active engagement of environmental auditing and enforcement;
 4. Clear and coordinated mandates and roles, across and within institutions;
 5. Accessible, fair, impartial, timely and responsive dispute resolution mechanisms, including developing specialized expertise in environmental adjudication, and innovative environmental procedures and remedies;
 6. Recognition of the mutually reinforcing relationship between human rights and the environment; and
 7. Specific criteria for the interpretation of environmental law.

What is fascinating about such ‘*high level*’ meetings and decisions arrived at is that the focus is on the application of laws that do not exist, since apart for the long list of soft laws in the form of MEAs, no substantive international environmental law has seen the light of day yet.

Moreover, in September 2016, the Prosecutor of the International Criminal Court formally published a new prosecutorial strategy, which included a commitment to ‘*give particular consideration to prosecuting Rome Statute crimes that are committed by means of, or that result in the illegal exploitation of natural resources.*’ (OTP Policy Paper, PARA41, 2016).

However, analysing the Policy Paper, Pereira (2020) Associate Professor at Cardiff University, UK observes that:

But despite the excitement of some international environmental and criminal lawyers, academics and NGOs following the publication of the OTP policy paper, as of March 2020 (i.e. three and a half years since the publication of the 2016 OTP policy paper), no investigations or prosecutions have been initiated by the OTP for war crimes, crimes against humanity or genocide in which environmental damage, illegal natural resources exploitation or land grabbing were regarded to be aggravating circumstances in the case selection and investigation criterion.

Another academic exercise? Nothing has changed in taking criminality beyond the concept of crimes that affect mainly humans, and the immediate human environment, and mainstream criminology has hardly ever given due consideration to those persisting types of crimes commonly practiced, and which slowly and irrevocably destroys the natural environment that humans depend on. As such, environmental crime, and the study of environmental criminology has remained solely human-centred, that is anthropocentric, stressing the belief that legal instruments should principally protect humans by ensuring an acceptable, liveable environment, but hardly recognising the necessity for legal frameworks that prevent destroying or modifying that environment.

South (2008), Sollund (2008) and White (2011) have discussed the concept of crime at length, and pinpointed how it relates to a breach of law, yet eco-global harms such as those committed by states and corporations, often eclipse the scope and reach of criminal law. In their analysis the authors refer to how laws and regulations which actually uphold and legitimize intolerable exploitation of non-human animals and of nature simply are,

Passed by means of the legislation processes supported by capitalist and consumerist interests, despite the increasing importance of environmental issues in modern contexts.

In his treatise ‘*The Conceptual Contours of Green Criminology*,’ White (2013b) discusses how the majority of environmental crime scholars within the green criminology perspective concentrate on exposing specific types of criminal or harmful environmental actions or

omissions, providing detailed descriptions and analyses of such criminal activities through the compilation of statistics rather than legal frameworks.

Regarding such statistics, Cao and Wyatt (2016) inform it is estimated that the monetary value of all forms of transnational organized environmental crime is worth between \$70 and \$213 billion annually, as established by Nellemann et al. (2014), making them, as described by Interpol (2012):

Currently one of the most profitable forms of criminal activity taking place throughout the world.

Due to their '*extraordinary extent and volume*,' environmental/ecological crimes are '*emerging as very serious global threats that cannot be underestimated any longer*,' concludes the 2012 Interpol Report. Discussing the extent of global environmental criminal activities for profit, Lynch and Stretesky (2014) declare that the scourge is becoming,

The biggest crimes in the history of the world. No other crimes have threatened the existence of the entire planet.

A necessity, and probably a difficulty one too arises when separating different types of environmental crimes with a view of enacting laws that would target specific types of environmental crimes in terms of definition. In assessing the seriousness of such crimes, mapping profiles of the criminals involved in any of those specific types of crimes is yet another difficult task. Randa (2014) observes that traditionally, exploring crime has concentrated on the sociological or psychological perspective, focusing on understanding criminality, or the sum of motivations, drives, pushes and pulls driving an individual toward criminal behaviour. Environmental criminologists, on the other hand, seek to understand and explore crime by focusing on the criminal event by concerning themselves more with the places, spaces, and objects that either facilitate or prevent a crime from occurring; in other words exploring the fields of criminology.

Despite the seriousness and enormity of the situation, Randa (2014) finds that too many criminologists have long ignored this topic, leading to a '*woefully low*' quantity of discussions on green crimes and environmental justice, as established earlier by Zilney et al. (2006). Rather than fumbling around with statistics and a multitude of regulations, a number of scholars find that criminalising environmental/ecological crimes, or green crimes within one aspect of criminology (green criminology) may resolve most of the legal and administrative problems encountered to this day.

Vervaele and van Uhm (2016), of *The International Association of Penal Law* similarly recognise an urgent need for legal protection of the environment, one that should lead to a discussion on '*the international regulatory framework for the protection of the environment and on the criminal enforcement dimension of it*.' They recognise that even if the international community has been very active in discussing regulatory protection of the environment through the drafting of policies, it has failed to integrate the criminal enforcement dimension in its policy circles. As early as 1998, *The Convention on the Protection of the Environment* organised by The Council of Europe (now The European Union) is one of the rare exceptions, but the Convention has, after just over two decades, not yet entered into force due to the absence of the necessary number of ratifications, and obviously objections from those with vested interests. It appears even if States have the power to regulate and enforce laws against environmental offences, their enforcement

capacity depends upon administrative regulations, and upon infringements of administrative licenses and license conditions, and the power of lobbyists.

The discussion of Faure (2017) of RECIEL, elaborates on how criminalizing an environmental offence can, in certain cases, be an effective and dissuasive way to achieve proper implementation of environmental law. However, there are large differences between the criminal sanctions provided for environmental offences across the globe, and often existing criminal sanctions are not sufficiently stringent to ensure a high level of environmental protection, claims the author. Similarly, the capacity of governments to enforce criminal law greatly varies. Faure finds that this is particularly true in many of the least developed countries, where very little development support has gone to strengthen the enforcement and judicial sector. Indeed, one of the biggest differences between many industrialized countries and the least developed, is the much larger proportion of police compared to the prosecuting or judicial sector. For example, reveals Faure (2017), in North America 44% of the allocated budget is spent on courts and prosecutions, and 56% on police, while in the countries in southern Africa only 16% is spent on prosecution/courts and 84% on police,.

To this day, developments in environmental/ecological crimes appear to have concentrated on identifying and quantifying such crimes in monetary terms, but hardly in terms of biological losses or ecosystem degradation. In their discourse on developments in environmental crime Gerben and Johson (2018) conclude that:

Intellectual challenges in criminology should question why and how the physical environment has an impact on individual and group behaviour, and how and why the physical and social environment influences the emergence of crime. Crime prevention, examines the idea of altering the environment in order to prevent crime.

While Gerben and Johson ask pertinent questions about the cause, Nobles (2019) finds that the current body of literature on the topic of environmental crime is bigger and better than ever, but the question of whether criminology/criminal justice scholars make a difference in this area is another matter entirely. Nobles suggest that:

Environmental crime must move away from the fringes into the criminological mainstream,

At this stage in the development of international environmental law, or the lack of it, questions are still being asked by scholars as to the reasons for lack of goodwill and reasons for stagnancy. There are a number of types of penal provisions used as enforcement measures in international environmental conventions; some are of a character as to be part of the field of international criminal law. Cho (2000) remarks that although a general international criminal law has been discussed and under consideration for a number of years, environmental protection through criminal law at the supranational level still encounters opposition.

According to the earlier observations of Palmer (1992) and the reflections of Cho (2000), doubts about the reality of international criminal law '*in the material sense of the word*' ultimately rest on scepticism about the reality of a genuine international community. In other words, as Uhlmann (2009) concludes in his discussion:

There is no international super legislature to establish international environmental criminal laws and no effective international mechanism with enforcement authority, and except for international war crime trials, the practice of international courts and tribunals cannot be adduced as evidence of the recognition in international customary law of anything even

faintly resembling the phenomenon of international environmental crimes or of an international environmental criminal law *stricto sensu*.

As opposed to the declaration of Nobles (2019), criminal justice scholars have been busy over the past decades in trying to recommend ways of curtailing environmental crime through effective judicial precepts. However, even before reaching that stage there is a need to identify:

3. The perpetrators of such crimes;
4. The causes of environmental/ecological crime; and
5. The most appropriate legal direction to follow.

When it comes to perpetrators, it is now established that both corporate and other illegal activities pose a significant threat to the welfare of the natural environment and communities simultaneously, and in analyzing and discussing the negative environmental impact of corporations, Mokhiber and Weissman (1999) declare that:

Given the pervasive presence of corporations in a wide range of activities in our society, and the impact of their actions on a much wider group of people than are affected by individual action, the potential for both economic and physical harm caused by a corporation is great.

Discussing the association of national and transnational corporations with activities directly linked to environmental/ecological harm, the perception of corporate crime has become an integral part of environmental crime and environmental criminology studies, and Mokhiber and Weissman (1999) further elaborate on corporate crime as being:

Crimes committed either by a corporation (i.e., a business having a separate legal personality from the natural person that manage its activities), or by individuals acting on behalf of a corporation or other business entity.

There have been numerous definitions of corporate environmental/ecological crime, most targeting specific crimes, but an all encompassing one from Mokhiber and Weissman (1999) stipulates that:

Corporate environmental/ecological crime refers to criminal offenses that are committed by corporations during the course of legitimate business activities, the crimes being often non-violent. But sometimes violence is also indirectly resorted to, as in the murder of environmentalists putting themselves in the way of some corporate projects.

Another definition of business-related environmental harm proposed by Beirne and South (2007) centres on:

The abuse and exploitation of ecological systems, including animal life; corporate disregard for land, air, and water quality; profiteering from trades and practices that destroy lives and leaves a legacy of damage for subsequent generations.

With the notion that environmental crimes are continuously being committed, and on the increase too, Ward (2001) questions the contribution of existing legal frameworks and the adequacy of existing legal principles as a vehicle for determining the complex issues of transnational corporate accountability that lie at the heart of the contemporary corporate responsibility objectives. Ivanović (2010) rightly argues that:

It is not difficult to argue that environmental crimes, which destroy natural capital and reduce ecosystem resilience, including the socio-ecological ecosystems of which humans are an integral part, are threats to national security.

The element of ‘*threat to national security*’ does not appear to have generated much international attention or discussion, except in the case of threat to future generations. These

are the salient issues that should have been addressed by politics, policy makers, and lawmakers, but appear to have escaped their attention, claims Ivanović (2010)

In a discussion about '*Legal Corporate Crimes*' and what he terms '*Lawful but awful*' Passas (2005), observes that:

By concentrating on what is officially defined as illegal or criminal, a more serious threat to society is left out. This threat is caused by corporate practices that are within the letter of the law and yet have multiple adverse social consequences. Thus, just when more effective regulatory action and oversight is imperative, the global neo-liberal agenda and practice promotes de-regulation and a further reduction of the role of the state. Not only does this have criminogenic consequences of its own, it furthers types of misconduct undermining democratic processes and sustainable economic growth.

What Passas did not stress upon is that invariably '*democratic processes*' in the South are undermined, while '*economic growth*' in the North is accentuated, through such environmental/ecological corporate criminal activities, and hence the '*neo-liberal agenda and practice*' that appears to have taken roots in the economies of the North.

On the other hand, Cullen and Agnew (2011) find while many corporations do play by the rules, others regard attainment of the corporate goal (profit) as achievable only by breaking the law, similar to the prior observation of Brack (2002) in that:

Too often, corporations choose to do business with whoever can provide services at cut-rate prices.

Earlier, Szasz (1986) discussed why corporations and even states are too often engaged in activities detrimental to both the environment and associated communities, concluding that:

Any system of environmental laws and regulations intended to provide a social good and protect against environmental catastrophe, would at the same time impose significant costs on businesses and runs counter to the corporate goal of maximizing profits, and would thus meet with strong opposition.

Additionally, Szasz (1986) finds the relationship between illegitimate and legitimate business to be more complex, in that it is '*one of mutually beneficial interdependence.*' The conclusion of Reiman and Leighton (2013) and Leighton (2013) reflects on such a situation where:

The point is not to create a system for corporations that mimics the over-criminalization and zero-tolerance approaches currently applied to individuals. Rather the goal is an enforcement pyramid for corporations and business entities that starts with effective regulation and extends to meaningful and proportionate criminal penalties for egregious and/or repeated violation.

However, even when harmful corporate acts are prohibited by regulations rather than criminal law, large fines are often measured in the hours it takes a corporation to generate an equivalent amount of revenue, and thus justify their economic reasons for ignoring regulations. Perversely, corporations may actually find it a disincentive to comply with environmental laws or regulations if compliance would generally raised their operational costs, which means that many corporations obeying the environmental laws, whether out of a sense of legal duty or public obligation, may find themselves disadvantaged and lose a competitive edge and consequently suffer in the marketplace to competitors willing to disregard environmental laws and regulations.

The discussions of Bell and McGillivray (2008) expounds on how wide and diverse the range of perpetrators of green crime have become, ranging from ‘*from solo flytippers to huge multinational corporations*’ and ‘*state actors,*’ arguably all busy harming the environment more than other marginalised or pseudo unidentified offenders.

The authors propose that environmental laws should challenge the continuing traditional conventional concept that:

1. Crime is the conduct of the poor and the powerless, as proposed and discussed by Reiman (1995), and
2. Criminology is mainly a science designed for controlling and oppressing the marginalised as discussed by Lynch (2000; 2020).

Discussing transnational environmental crime, White (2011) concludes the same is at the centre of eco-global criminology, and includes crimes related to pollution of air, water and land and crimes against wildlife, including illegal trade in animal parts as well as live animals. It also includes those harms that pose threats to the environment more generally, such as global warming. White concludes that:

Political economy is at the heart of the exploitation of animals and environments and that property values assigned to animals and the environment are important in a capitalist system, and thus the rise in thought-provoking discussion of species justice issues and conflicting attitudes towards the protection or exploitation of animals.

Measuring environmental crime in terms of intensity or seriousness of consequences is not an easy task either. The studies of Gibbs and Simpson (2009) establish that the problem of measuring corporate crime rates has been the subject of debate, speculation and practicality for decades, largely stemming from the complexity of measuring this type of crime. Examining corporate environmental crime poses challenges and creates opportunities for advancing the discussion of corporate crime rates, but criminologists are less familiar with environmental data, observe the authors.

However, whether crimes should be measured and quantified before applying appropriate regulations and laws should never be any reason for hesitancy and laxity. Simpson et al. (2013) suggest that current policy machineries do not fully mitigate offending risks and may indicate that a one-size-fits-all policy should be regarded as short sighted and ineffective. The authors further discuss how regulators can frame environmental messages, utilize scarce resources, and align regulatory levers with specific types of offenses, leaving a necessity to untangle whether the processes and control mechanisms adopted today are similar for other types of corporate crimes.

In one of his discussions about the causes of environmental crime, White (2013) observes that the systemic causal chains that underpin much environmental harm are located at the level of the global political economy, within which transnational corporation stand as the central social force, and this is reflected in the ‘*pressing together of the local-global at a practical level.*’ The reality is that international systems of production, distribution and consumption generate and reinforce environmental harms, and at the same time reward those who perpetrate them.. White (2013) suggests that what the world needs is,

A basic premise of green or environmental criminology to take environmental harm seriously, and conceptualization of harm that goes beyond conventional understanding of crime.

Amnesty International (2014) admits that absence of a universally recognised legal definition of international environmental crime renders prosecution of the offence difficult, if not

impossible mainly due to the lack of binding rules on criminal liability of multinational corporations, recognised as the main perpetrators of ‘*eco-crime*.’ It has been suggested that the powerful influence that multinational corporations wield over some governments, or State complicity in the unlawful actions of some corporations are the main problems, according to Amnesty International. De Vos (2017) of Amnesty International sees a need to end all types of impunity, to hold corporations accountable for their illegal actions, and to bring justice to the victims of international environmental crime, which still remains a challenging objective. Obviously to prove that crime has been committed, there must be victims, even when such victims have no voice.

One question that has often been asked is what happens to nations that surrender ever-growing economic and political power to the globally super rich and the mammoth multinational corporations they control? And what can people from around the world do to resist the criminality and victimization perpetrated by multinationals, and generated by the prevailing global political economy? Barak (2017), Professor of Criminology and Criminal Justice at Eastern Michigan University, USA, has examined an array of multinational crimes (corporate, environmental, financial, and state) and their state-legal responses, and outlines policies and strategies for revolutionizing these contradictory relations of capital reproduction, criminality, and unsustainability. Although much of the information provided by Barak could act as a catalyst for criminology studies and crime prevention, connectivity appears to remain a problem among environmental scholars.

The influence of corporations, or rather capitalism on states and their ability to shape regulations and laws in their favour is nothing new. Stretesky, Long and Lynch (2015) have discussed how the expansion of capitalism have shaped environmental law related to crime and justice. According to them:

Capital does not tally the costs of the damage it produces as part of any of its ledgers of production, nor does it possess the long-run vision or the ability to step outside of its present-oriented self-interest that drives profit-making to consider the needs of future generations.

Brittle and Hebert (2019), discussing the reasons as to why corporations and corporate executives produce so much harm and devastation and why states regularly fail to discipline corporations in the face of such serious crimes, conclude that what is of concern are the existing and persisting ‘*regimes of permission*’ that make corporate crime possible and which allow corporations to avoid criminal justice scrutiny. Brittle and Hebert find that ‘*laws intended to curb corporate offending paradoxically reinforce corporate impunity*;’ additionally, ‘*neoliberal*’ beliefs that corporations are inherently good and law-abiding serve to differentiate corporate offending from ‘*real crimes*.’

It should also become clear that whenever there is crime, there are also victims. In a discussion about victims of environmental crime, Skinnider (2011) explains how identifying the perpetrator in environmental cases and establishing criminal liability can be extremely difficult, since the chain of causation from perpetrator to harm can be long and complex, involving more than nationals from the same country, as established by the UN-Interpol Report of 2016, and victims are of the silent type, the voiceless. The more difficult it is to identify perpetrators, the more difficult it is to pursue and punish them. Possible perpetrators include individuals, collectives, corporations, governments, and organized criminal groups, explains Skinnider. There might even an interconnection between multinational corporations, corrupt state officials and organised crime, claims Skinnider (2011).

The concept of '*Victimology*' developed by some scholars have been discussed by Hough (1987), Dignan (2005), Johnson (2017) and Hall (2017), and these scholars have exposed yet another of the unresolved issues in environmental law issues: '*critical victimology*,' and its expanded notions of victimhood beyond simple criminal classifications. In an analysis and discussion about environmental victimisation and violence, Williams (1996) explains how reckless actions from the perpetrators may affect three generations, past, present and future, concluding that:

The key element of violence is physical force, and environmental victims are defined as past, present, or future generations who are injured due to change in the chemical, physical, microbiological, or psychosocial environment produced by deliberate or reckless individuals or by collective human acts.

One issue that continually creeps up is whether only three generations of humans should be at the centre of concern, or generations of other members of the natural environment too should be part of the equation. Drawing from the works of Hall (2014) and White and Heckenberg (2014), White (2015) defines environmental victimology as:

Environmental victimology refers to the study of the social processes and institutional responses pertaining to victims of environmental crime. It is a new area of criminological concern, and it can be intellectually located as a subset of '*green criminology*', itself a relatively new development.

Moving from perpetrators and causes, the obvious next issue would be how to put and end to environmental/ecological crimes through the precepts of environmental/ecological law. Hillyard and Tombs (2007) have been influential in pushing the boundaries of how criminologists think about and define the concept of '*crime*'. They were among the first within the field of criminology to engage in a thorough examination of the notion of '*social harm*' and have suggested that it might form a broader more inclusive picture of the causes of human suffering and environmental global harm than traditional studies of '*crime*' and '*criminals*.' These should also include consideration of the activities of local and national states and corporations, political regimes and ideologies, and social institutions, including criminal justice systems, recommend Hillyard and Tombs.

According to the analyses of White (2008), increasing attention has been paid by criminologists to the natural environment and to criminal activities that lead to environmental degradation over the last three decades. Researchers in the field have variously labelled such types of crimes as '*eco-critical criminology*' (Lynch and Stretesky, 2007), '*eco-global criminology*,' '*green criminology*' (Lynch, 1990; South, 1998; Ruggiero and South, 2010) and, more recently, '*conservation criminology*' (Gibbs et al., 2010) and '*ecocide*' (Higgins (2010; 2012). However, whatever be the appellation, the objective remain instituting legal frameworks within the crime prevention spheres to curtail environmental/ecological crimes globally. Researchers within the field have made steady progress towards the application of criminological theories of offending and crime prevention strategies to such activities. From a critical perspective, Pepper, (1993) notes that criminology has also cast light on the power imbalances inherent in the labelling of certain polluting activities as '*criminal*', which is invariably tied up with the economic goals of corporate actors and states as a whole, at the same time falling within the scope of environmental/ecological crimes at both the national and global levels.

Green International Criminology or simply '*Green Criminology*' appears to have been the accepted term qualifying crimes against the environment, and has been recognised as the main cause of harms, sometimes irreversible, against the environment, or natural systems.

The concept of '*Green Criminology*' was first introduced by Lynch (1990), expanded upon in 1992 by Frank and Lynch in a publication titled *Corporate Crime, Corporate Violence: A Primer*, leading to the term being first coined by Nigel South in the late 1990s, and it encompasses environmental crimes that have been referred to and discussed as '*eco-critical criminology*' (Seis, 1993), '*conservation criminology*' (Herbig and Joubert, 2006), '*eco-global criminology*' (White, 2009; 2011), and '*ecocide*' Higgins (2010).

While there may not be universal consensus about a name for this sub-field of criminology, or its perspective, criminologists most frequently employ the term '*green criminology*' to describe the study of crime, harm and injustice related to the environment and to species other than humans. Other suggestions that have appeared over the years include:

- Peacemaking criminology (Pepinsky and Quinney, 1991).
- Conservation criminology (Gibbs et al., 2010).
- Eco-crime suggested by Walters (2010).
- Eco-global criminology proposed by White (2011; 2012).

Other environmental or '*green*' criminologists, including Herbig and Joubert (2006) have opted for a change in approach, making it more '*biocentric*' or '*deep green*,' defining environmental harm as '*any human activity that disrupts a biotic system.*' Rather than '*environmental crime*,' that has been proposed by several scholars, Herbig and Joubert (2006) opt for '*conservation crime*' defining it as:

Any intentional or negligent human activity or manipulation that impacts negatively on the earth's biotic and/or abiotic natural resources, resulting in immediately noticeable or indiscernible (only noticeable over time) natural resource trauma of any magnitude

Environmental harms that are currently defined narrowly as crimes or illegal activities (i.e. violations of civil or regulatory law) clearly fall within the scope of conservation criminology, argue Herbig and Joubert (2006). Anthropogenic actions (or negligence) at the individual, collective, corporate and state levels that produce harm, or the potential of harm to people and the environment through the '*illegal manipulation and exploitation of natural resources*' should be included as well, propose the authors.

In apposition to green criminology and the proposition of conservation crime/conservation criminology of Herbig and Joubert (2006), a number of scholars have resorted to the concept of '*Conservation Criminology*' since issues arising from public perceptions of risk may also benefit from a conservation criminology framework. One area of concern of environmental interest groups and communities has been about the need to regulate the release of pharmaceuticals into the environment, discussed by Daughton (2003). Similarly, others have become increasingly concerned with the use of nanotechnology and its possible influence on the natural environment, discussed by Smita et al. (2012).

Assessing, managing and developing risk communication strategies, intended to influence citizen or corporate behaviour through deliberative processes that include scientific analysis and stakeholder concern fall within the scholarly domain of risk, explains Smita et al. (2012).. However, if scientific assessment and stakeholder concern create a serious consideration of systems to regulate nanotechnology, the issue will fall within the scope of conservation criminology, conclude the authors.

With the goal of moving beyond traditional legalist definitions of environmental crime, Cho (2003) proposes that the focus of conservation criminology begin with assessment of

environmental risks. One advantage of doing so is that it builds upon existing known risks that provide systematic tools for assessing the degree of risk for human health, natural resources and the environment in general, contends Cho.

In the domain of technical assessments, Arvai (2007) defines risk as:

A function of the probability of exposure to a hazard and the expected consequences of the hazard if the exposure is realized.

Discussing their proposal for conservation criminology, Gibbs et al. (2010) observe that since environmental criminology studies have largely been left to other disciplines, the emergence of environmental or green criminology over the past decade marks a shift in this trend, but attempts to define a unique area of study have been extensively criticized. Gibbs et al. (2010) therefore propose an alternative: '*conservation criminology*,' designed to advance current discussions of green crime via the integration of criminology with natural resource disciplines and risk and decision sciences.

Gibbs et al. (2010) further propose that three disciplines should form the foundation of conservation criminology:

1. Criminal justice and criminology,
2. Risk and decision analysis, and
3. Natural resource conservation and management.

The authors believe the synergy of these disciplines can address a variety of environmental risks that occur at their intersection.

Discouraging on the global aspects of green criminology, or *eco-global criminology*, White (2011), refers to it as an analytical framework that focuses on the interrelated matters of the ecological (the '*eco*'), the transnational (the '*global*'), and justice (the '*criminology*'). Its substantive focus is transgressions against ecosystems, humans and animals. As such, as well as its global perspective on issues and events, White (2011) defines eco-global criminology as:

Eco-global criminology refers to a framework of analysis where the emphasis is on the ecological, the transnational and questions of justice. The substantive focus is transgressions against ecosystems, humans and animals.

White (2011) further emphasizes the need to distinguish between environmental crimes as outlined by legal systems and through various forms of environmental harms, particularly those with global implications, and expand the scope of eco-global criminology beyond the existing narrow legal definitions. Basing their arguments upon the Eco-Justice conceptions of harm (discussed by Venkatasamy, 2002), White (2011) and Stanislas (2012) argue that such a necessity invariably focuses on transgressions against environments, non-human species and humans, leading to the concept of green criminology.

Sollund (2012) proposes that '*because of the multivariate character of problems relating to eco-global crimes*,' it should be deemed necessary to expand the boundaries of green criminology as a discipline, and White (2012) develops this theme further by showing that environmental harms often '*transcend the normal boundaries of jurisdiction, geography and social divide*.' As a discipline, the perspective of what environmental/ecological crime is about and what should be perceived as a crime, as well as the notions of harm and justice, it

needs to be expansive enough to pave the way towards just redressment and justified punishment.

However, Green Criminology (GC) as proposed by Lynch (1990) has remained the accepted term in environmental/ecological crime studies, but remains a field of study that did not originally attract many environmental/ecological legal scholars. Thirty years later, there is still no agreement concerning the exact definition of the term '*green crime*,' one that may lead to the concept of green criminology. The term can vary significantly across green scholars, and definitions have numerous and wide-ranging meanings making it difficult to critically analyze each of them without creating further confusion in treating the criminal aspects of environmental/ecological crimes. What marks out green criminology from other green criminological perspectives, explains South and Brisman (2013) and White and Heckenberg (2014), is the attention given to '*specifically ecological considerations of harm rather than criminal definitions*.'

Originally, green crime was defined by Lynch (1990) as including:

1. Harms caused to living beings through the creation of environmental hazards;
2. Environmental harms that exist at the local and global levels;
3. Outcomes that are tied to corporate and state crimes; and
4. GC as the subject matter of radical criminology and political economic theory/analysis, and its concern with class analysis.

As early as 1990, Lynch brought into the field of green criminology the responsibility of both states and corporations, leading into the concept of corporate and transnational crimes. To be more explicit in defining green crime and green criminology, White (2008) proposes dividing such crimes and criminal activities into three main categories:

1. Brown crimes or environmental harms in urban landscapes;
2. White crimes related to new technologies; and
3. Green crimes, restricted to environmental harms.

As proposed by Ruggiero and South (2013), Green Criminology (GC) can be defined as:

A framework of intellectual, empirical and political orientations toward primary and secondary harms, offences and crimes that impact in a damaging way on the natural environment, diverse species (human and non-human) and the planet.

On the other hand White (2014) defines green criminology as:

Generally speaking, green criminology takes as its focus issues relating to the environment (in the widest sense possible) and harm (as defined in ecological as well as strictly legal terms).

Although Green Crime is basically Environmental Crime, Nigel South (2016) prefers defining Green Crime as:

Crime against the environment, linked to globalisation and the idea of transnational boundaries on the premise that regardless of the division of the nation states, the planet is one unified eco-system which is global rather than local.

While green criminologists are all interested in harms to the environment, Halsey (2004) and White and Heckenberg, (2014) recognise that *Anthropocentrism*, the human-centered perspective emphasizing on '*the biological, mental and moral superiority of humans over other living and non-living entities*' has probably been the greatest stumbling block to the evolution of environmental/ecological or green law. As Halsey and White (1998) explain, for anthropocentrists:

Nature is viewed instrumentally-as something to be appropriated, processed, consumed and disposed of in ways that best suit human needs in the present.

From an anthropocentric perspective, humans are viewed as separate from, rather than part of the world's ecosystems and the integrity of these non-human ecosystems or entities (air, plants, animals, soil, water) are of concern only insofar as they stand to benefit the human species. On the other hand, White and Heckenberg (2014) postulates that *Ecocentrism* refuses to place humanity either above or below the rest of nature. On the contrary, it is based on the premise that humans and their activities are inextricably interconnected with the rest of the natural world.

White and Heckenberg further state:

The unique capacity for human beings to develop and deploy methods of production which have global consequences means that humans also have an explicit responsibility to ensure that such production methods do not exceed the ecospheric limits of the planet - a responsibility that extends to both human and non-human life

Discussing green crime, Beirne and South (2007) also create a specific, though not exhaustive list of behaviours that illustrates the numerous ways in which green crimes occur at the political and economic levels, including:

- Abuse and exploitation of ecosystems, including animal life;
- Corporate disregard for damage to land, air and water quality;
- Profiteering from trades and practices that destroy lives and which leave a legacy of damage for subsequent generations;
- Military actions in war that adversely impact the environment and animals;
- New challenges to international treaties and to the emerging field of bio-ethics, such as bio-piracy; illicit markets in nuclear materials; and legal monopolization of natural resources (e.g., privatization of water, patenting of natural products, etc.) leading to the division between the resources of the rich and the resource impoverished and the prospects of a new form of conflict, harm, injury and damage;
- The institutional, socially acceptable human domination of animals in agribusiness, in slaughterhouses, and abattoirs, in so-called scientific experimentation and, in less obviously direct ways, in sports, colleges and schools, zoos, aquaria, and circuses.

Three decades after its introduction, the scope of GC has today become much broader, not simply restricted to ecological harms and their origins, but also draws attention to:

1. The frameworking, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws;
2. Resolving the problem of environmental justice; and
3. The ways in which all living beings, humans, nonhuman, and the living Earth System are victimized by ecological harms.

As previously indicated by White (2008), within green criminology there are three broad approaches to justice, each with their own specific conceptions of what is harmful, including:

- Human rights and environmental justice – in which environmental rights are seen as an extension of human or social rights so as to enhance the quality of human life, now and into the future.
- Ecological citizenship and ecological justice – in which it is acknowledged that humans are merely one component of complex ecosystems that should be preserved for their own sake via the notion of the rights of the environment.

- Animal rights and species justice – in which environmental harm is constructed in relation to the place of nonhuman animals within environments and their intrinsic right to not suffer abuse, whether this be one-on-one harm, institutionalised harm or harm arising from human actions that affect climates and environments on a global scale.

Additionally, contends White (2008), since Green Crime goes beyond political borders, it should be further divided as:

1. Primary green crimes, those crimes which constitute harm inflicted on the environment and, by extension, those that inflict harm on people because of damage to the environment; environmental victims who suffer health or other problems when the land, water or air they interact with is polluted, damaged or destroyed.
2. Secondary or ‘*symbiotic*’ green crime that grows out of the flouting of rules that seek to regulate environmental disasters (Discussed by Carrabine et al. 2004).

Analysing the proposals of White (2008), South and Brisman (2013) recognise four main categories of primary green crimes:

- Crimes of air pollution,
- Crimes of deforestation,
- Crimes of species decline and animal rights, and,
- Crimes of water pollution.

Going back to the reflections of White, South (2016) provides two examples of secondary green crimes:

- Violence against environmental groups (e.g. the French attack on the Greenpeace ship, the Rainbow Warrior).
- Bribery/organised crime to avoid environmental regulations.

Green criminologists have also engaged in the study of existing and proposed environmental law and regulation. Fitzgerald and Baralt (2010) and South (2016) discuss the failures, inadequacies, and inefficacies which may stem from avoidance of corporate, state, and personal responsibility regarding environmental crimes, or harms, or threats, as Walters (2010) remarks are all due to:

From an implementation deficit due to a country's lack of financial and technical resources, limited expertise in international environmental law, inability to keep pace with the rapid expansion in treaties, overstretched and under-resourced ministries.

Since much of the actual harm caused to the natural environment has always been perceived to be legitimate and lawful, Rob White (2013a;b) finds that though environmental criminology can be a highly contested concept, it can be achieved through a combination of embedding harmful practices into everyday activities. Green criminology, claims White, is premised on the need to take environmental harm seriously, translating into the conceptualisation of a type of harm that goes beyond conventional understandings of crime, as has been discussed and proposed by Beirne and South (2007) and South and Brisman (2014). Green criminologists generally agree that destructive and damaging human activities that harm environments warrant greater attention than has hitherto been the case within criminology. There are already a plethora of laws and conventions that deal with environmental crimes and harms, yet Beirne and South (2007), South and Brisman (2013) and White (2013) finds that very little criminological attention had been given to analysis of

how these are actually working, or how best to ‘*apply criminological insights from areas such as crime prevention to environmental crime matters.*’

Wildlife crime should also be a core concern of green crime/green criminology propounds Sollund (2012), Cao and Wyatt (2013), van Uhm (2017) and Nurse (2017) A number of green criminological discourses are concerned with wildlife trafficking and the illegal trade in wildlife and wildlife parts, particularly trafficking in endangered species (discussed by Schneider, 2008). However, it is only recently that the illegal killing of wildlife, particularly within farming and ranching areas, has caught the attention of green criminological scholars, and included into the green crimes portfolio. Killing of large predators such as wolves has been characterized as a form of resistance by some scholars (discussed by von Essen 2017), and illustrates the conflict between conservation and animal protection ideologies and the needs of rural communities, with total disregard for the respect to life that wildlife needs and is entitled to.

Over the years, green criminology has become a fast expanding field within criminology with healthy roots in critical criminology (Lynch 1990; Sollund 2012; South and Brisman 2013;) and a wide range of concerns regarding legal and illegal harms against the environment (Beirne and South 2007; Sollund 2015; Walters et al. 2013; White 2008, 2013a,b; White and Heckenberg 2014). To date, green criminologists have investigated the causes and consequences of environmental crimes and harms, as well as the meaning thereof and the responses thereto (e.g., law enforcement, punishment (or the lack thereof)). Reflecting on the progress of environmental criminology, South (2014) states that:

The seriousness of crimes against the environment has not received full acknowledgement as a field of study in criminology despite being a matter of global significance.

In spite of the support so far, green criminology is not easily categorized given that it draws together a number of different perspectives as well as theoretical and ideological conceptions. Thus, rather than there being one distinct green criminology, it is rather an umbrella term for a criminology concerned with the general neglect of ecological issues within criminology, observe Lynch and Stretesky, (2014), as well as the incorporation of green perspectives within mainstream criminology. Indeed, as Lynch and Stretesky succinctly state:

As criminologists we are not simply concerned that our discipline continues to neglect green issues, we are disturbed by the fact that, as a discipline, criminology is unable to perceive the wisdom of taking green harms more seriously, and the need to reorient itself in ways that make it part of the solution to the large global environmental problems we now face as the species that produces those problems..

Instead, and as proposed by White (2013), GC ‘*tends to begin with a strong sensitivity toward crimes of the powerful,*’ since the main motivation behind environmental harm has been shown to be economic and happens in order to maintain a capitalist production system based upon continual growth as elaborated upon by Stretesky et al. (2014). Growth invariably comes at the expense of the environment that provides the materials for production, thus leading the way to corporate/transnational environmental/ecological crimes, or green crimes.

Discoursing on how environmental harm caused by corporations and states in pursuit of profit are more often hidden because they control criminalisation, Passas (2005), Tombs and Whyte (2009, 2015) and Kramer (2020) have examined, analyzed and elaborated on the destructive relationship between the fossil fuel industry and states that ‘*allows catastrophic climate change and its victimisation to continue unabated*’. However, it should not be assumed all green crimes are purely economic in origin, and Cao and Wyatt (2013; 2016),

and Brisman and South (2019) have analyzed, discussed and revealed how animal abuse and cruelty as well as demand for wildlife products and pollution can be motivated by status seeking and cultures, and these are also activities that fall within the environmental/ecological aspects of green criminology.

The conclusion of White (2013), after several studies related to environmental or eco-global crimes, is that undeniably corporations are the chief environmental offenders, more often with existing legal and political resources shielding their transgressions from law enforcement. White finds that in some cases, national government and public bodies officials are direct perpetrators of environmental crimes (either by way of commission or omission) or through corruption, especially in collusion with powerful corporations. In addition, no country is immune from government officials-corporate collusion and corruption in the commission of environmental crimes. Prioritising the interests of corporations/businesses over those of the local citizens, especially in relation to the access, use, and disposal of resources, can increase economic hardships and result in civil unrest and disruptions.

Lynch and Stretsky (2014) distinguish between two perspectives on Green Crime: the '*corporate perspective*' (the legal-procedural approach) and the '*environmental justice perspective*' (the socio-legal approach). For these authors the corporate perspective recognizes the influence of corporate power structures on the creation or delineation of those unauthorized acts or omissions that violate the law and are therefore subject to criminal prosecution and sanctions, as long as the instruments for prosecution exist. And for a definition of green Crime, Stretsky et al.,(2014) suggest:

Acts that cause or have the potential to cause significant harm to ecological systems for the purpose of increasing or supporting production.

Similar to any other area of criminological research, and borrowing from the philosophy of Gaia of Lovelock and Margulis, discussed by Lovelock (1988), GC tends to also address the definition of its main focus, green crimes, not a simple nor settled matter yet, and Lynch et al. (2017) proposes that the very first step would be by asking in the first place '*What is a green crime?*' then moving to three important elements:

1. Studying green crimes requires measuring them. Measuring green crimes is not just important but necessary.
2. Studying green crimes requires addressing legal statutes and law enforcement mechanisms that define and control green crimes.
3. Quantifying GC, which has for long been largely descriptive, theoretical, philosophical, and qualitative.

White (2017) elaborates on what he termed '*the four ways*' of eco-global criminology, and discusses the importance of recognising and acting in regards to the differences evident in:

- Ways of being (ontology),
- Ways of knowing (epistemology),
- Ways of doing (methodology), and
- Ways of valuing (axiology).

The discussions of White (2017) establish the aim of eco-global criminology/green criminology in yet another statement:

To bring some sensibility to inconsistencies in environmental crime and environmental law; and provide a coherent, critical narrative to the commonsense embedded in those concrete practices that are rapidly destroying the very basis of life as we know it.

From the studies of Nurse (2017) it transpires that green criminology/or eco-global criminology, encompassing broad green perspectives among other things, provide a mechanism for rethinking the study of criminal laws, ethics, crime, criminal behaviour and regulatory approaches to environmental problems. Within the growing yet now established discipline of green criminology, Nurse finds there exists different conceptions on what constitutes a crime, what should be perceived as crime, and how it should be labelled or described.

Beirne (2018) propose that green criminology should address pressing issues such as animal abuse, biodiversity loss; the extraction and exploitation of natural resources, deforestation, pollution of air, land and water by private individuals, corporations, states and the military, the diverse ways in which state-corporate collusion and weak and/or failed states contribute to a host of interconnected green crimes, and the challenges posed by global warming and climate change to life itself on our '*shared planet*' (discussed previously by Benton, 1998). Beirne et al. conclude that:

Importantly, green criminology has provided the broad field of criminology with a way to confront harms (whether defined as 'crimes' or not) that affect the planet as a whole, particular natural environments and species other than humans.

The study of green crimes and the expansion of the green criminological spheres continue to expand, and recently Brisman and South (2019) list the extended types of inquiries that green criminologists undertake with respect to environmental harm, and with respect to the following types of harm:

- Air pollution and water issues (access, pollution, scarcity);
- Animal abuse, animal rights and animal welfare, including the legal and illegal trade in non-human animals;
- Crime and harm stemming from global warming and climate change;
- Food and agricultural crimes;
- Harm caused by the hazardous transport of e-waste and the illegal disposal of toxic waste; and
- Violations of workplace health and safety regulations that have environmentally damaging consequences.

And because Green Crime is becoming increasingly sophisticated, it is rising up the list of priorities for law enforcement agencies and regulators alike. Interpol and Europol recognize the wider links between Green Crime and transnational organised crime and terrorism. According to Interpol, the exploitation of natural resources by criminal networks, often in conflict areas, poses a threat to peace and security. Yet despite the increased focus on Green Crime, the fines and sanctions directed towards this illicit activity are far less than those related to anti-money laundering and the financing of terrorism. Given these disparities, raises a pertinent point: is it not time to re-calibrate the current legislative and enforcement regimes to take in to account the damage caused by these crimes and the risk they present for future generations?

Now a global industry, Green Crime and environmental crime are estimated to be worth up to \$258 billion a year, with wildlife crime alone being one of the top five most lucrative illegal (criminal) activities, after illegal drugs, human and weapons trafficking. The European Union has included environmental crime as a predicate offence under the 6th EU Anti-Money Laundering Directive (6AMLD). And the new Financial Action Task Force (FATF) priorities for 2020 will focus on the illegal wildlife trade.

However, turning the tide on Green Crime would require increased collaboration and effective cooperation across the public and private sectors, at the same time soliciting a concerted effort to bring big companies, regulators, politicians, and charities together in order to meet the challenge. More importantly, it would require these various organisations, often working in silos, to rally around a global mission statement.

Moving away from the sinuous route of criminalising environmental harms through criminological perceptions, it has also been proposed that such harms should be classified as the crime of Ecocide, much in the same way as the crime of Genocide has been recognised in international criminal law.

Ecocide as a crime against the environment was born out of the tragedy of the Vietnam war, when over a period of some 10 years the United States government sprayed 19 million gallons of powerful herbicides, including Agent Orange, across the countryside in Vietnam, Cambodia and Laos to expose enemy sanctuaries during the Vietnam War. Calls to criminalise ecocide date back to the 1970s when Yale biologist Arthur Galston invoked the destruction to call on the world to outlaw what he called '*Ecocide*,' following America's devastating use of the chemical '*Agent Orange*' in the Vietnam War. Analysed and discussed by Stellman and Stellman (2018), the enormous harm it caused to both the environment (destroying forests and decimating biodiversity) and humans (harming or killing thousands of people) sparked proposals for an international law against ecocide.

At the 1972 United Nations Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment, Mr Olof Palme, then Prime Minister of Sweden, spoke explicitly in his opening speech of the Vietnam War as a crime of '*ecocide*'. For the first time the Stockholm Conference focused international attention on environmental issues, especially in relation to environmental degradation and trans-boundary pollution.

In 1973, Professor Falk, professor emeritus of international law at Princeton University (USA), and Euro-Mediterranean Human Rights Monitor's Chairman of the Board of Trustees, published the proposed International Convention on the Crime of Ecocide, a draft containing a full analysis, definition and framework for the proposed ecocide law, justifying his proposal by declaring that:

.....man has consciously and unconsciously inflicted irreparable damage to the environment in times of war and peace.

The Draft Convention proposed by Falk based its propositions on the following:

- The commission of acts of ecocide is an international crime in violation of the spirit, letter and aims of the United Nations and, as such, is in direct violation of the Charter of the United Nations and violates the sense of minimum moral obligation prevailing in the world community;
- The protection of man's relation to natural ecosystems is a legal, moral obligation deserving of the highest respect and directly related to the prospects for human survival and social development;
- Any government, organization, group or individual that commits, plans, supports, or advocates ecocide shall be considered as committing an international crime of grave magnitude and as acting contrary to the laws of humanity and in violation of the ecological imperative.
- The forcible removal of human beings or animals from their habitual places of habitation to expedite the pursuit of military or industrial objectives.

The Draft Convention (Article I) states:

The Contracting Parties confirm that ecocide, whether committed in time of peace or in time of war, is a crime under international law which they undertake to prevent and to punish.

The Draft Convention further listed a number of recommendations of which the following should be mentioned:

Article III: The following acts shall be punishable

1. Ecocide;
2. Conspiracy to commit ecocide;
3. Direct and public incitement to ecocide;
4. Attempt to commit ecocide;
5. Complicity in ecocide.

Article V: The United Nations shall establish a Commission for the Investigation of Ecocide as soon as this Convention comes into force. This Commission shall be composed of fifteen experts on international law and assisted by a staff conversant with ecology.

Article VI: The Contracting Parties undertake to enact, in accordance with their respective Constitutions, the necessary legislation to give effect to the provisions of the present Convention and, in particular, to provide effective penalties for persons guilty of ecocide or any of the other acts enumerated in Article III.

Article VII: Persons charged with ecocide or any of the other acts enumerated in Article II shall be tried by a competent tribunal of the State in the territory of which the act was committed, or by such international penal tribunal as may have jurisdiction with respect to those Contracting Parties which shall have accepted its jurisdiction.

Professor Falk further declared that:

The increasing number of actors, their diversity, and the complexity of international life make it more difficult to rely upon procedures based on governmental consent to develop either binding new interpretations of old rules or the generation of new rules of international law.

However, for reasons not known, the draft International Convention on the Crime of Ecocide was shelved, and never referred to either in the United Nation's deliberations on environmental law, or any other international organisations deliberations on environmental crime, environmental criminology or environmental law. A follow up of the proposal from Professor Richard Falk in 1989 does not appear to have attracted the attention of international lawmakers.

Ecocide was later mentioned by the Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC, 1985) in an update to a Study, '*Cultural genocide, ethnocide and ecocide,*' and Benjamin Whitaker, Special Rapporteur of ECOSOC, noted that some members of the Sub-Commission have proposed that the definition of genocide be broadened to include '*ecocide,*' and re-defined as:

Adverse alterations, often irreparable, to the environment, for example through nuclear explosions, chemical weapons, serious pollution and acid rain, or destruction of the rain forest, which threaten the existence of entire populations, whether deliberately or with criminal negligence.

It can be noted that ECOSOC persists in associating environmental crimes with acts of war, which is far from what the crime of '*ecocide*' specifically represents.

The period between 1984 and 1996 proved to be an interesting journey during the formulation of the Code of Crimes of the Rome Statute, at which time there were propositions to include a law regarding extensive environmental damage. In 1991, the ILC created the *Draft Code of Crimes Against the Peace and Security of Mankind*. The initial draft Code contained 12 crimes, including an environmental crime, or a crime of ecocide. Article 26, '*Willful and Severe Damage to the Environment.*' of the Code stated,

An individual who willfully causes or orders the causing of widespread, long-term and severe damage to the natural environment shall, on conviction thereof, be sentenced.

During the ILC's 47th Session in 1995 a working group was established to examine covering environmental crimes in the Draft Code. However, over years of deliberations, the ILC appears to have sidelined the crime of ecocide in its vision. Consideration of whether to include in the Code '*acts causing serious damage to the environment*' as a crime of ecocide through Article 26 led some members to re-open the debate in 1996, and this time round debated whether ecocide was a crime of '*intent.*' Criticisms centred on the inclusion of the element of '*intent*' and on the fact that the final draft of Article 26 did not address environmental crime by name and it contained no reference to ecocide.

In 1996, the working group issued a report, recommending that environmental crimes should be included as:

1. A separate provision; or
2. A crime against humanity; or
3. A war crime

In yet another ILC meeting in 1996, Mr. Tomuschat, chairman of the ILC Commission, re-introduced the draft proposals that the working group had agreed upon on the issue of '*willful and severe damage to the environment.*' In the ILC's 48th session in 1996, Rapporteur Tomuschat suggested either to:

- Retain environmental crimes as a distinct and separate provision; or
- Include environmental crimes as an act of crimes against humanity; or
- Include environmental crimes as a war crime.

In yet another meeting of the ILC in 1996, the then Chairman, Mr Ahmed Mahiou, unilaterally decided to remove the crime of ecocide completely as a separate provision, without putting it to a vote to the Working Group. Thus, Article 26 was removed completely and somewhat mysteriously from the Code, and morphed into:

Intentionally causing widespread, long-term and severe damage to the natural environment within a war context.

The ILC's decision probably led Gray (1996) to sum up a discussion on the hide and seek game of the UN and the ILC regarding the crime of ecocide, concluding that:

Despite its reluctance to create new international crimes, a reluctance justified by the absence of enforcement machinery, the international community will soon realize that ecocide so menaces fundamental human rights and international peace and security that it must be treated with the same gravity as apartheid or genocide. Precise standards of causation, damage and culpability, and institutions to prosecute and punish offenders, will follow.

The ILC Draft Code (1996), an attempt to codify crimes that pose a serious threat to the peace and security of mankind, has been critically analysed and discussed by Allain and Jones (1997). Although observers and environmental activists have long bemoaned the absence of normative force behind the international instruments designed to protect the

environment, in their analysis Allain and Jones (1997) recognise that article 26 of the Code stressing on ‘*willfully causing or ordering the causing of widespread, longterm and severe damage to the natural environment*’ anticipates future attempts to safeguard the environment, and it is in this context that the criminalization of willful environmental destruction should be considered; additionally, the Code has identified five characteristics of environmental crime that should be explored further to qualify it as an international environmental crime, including:

1. Indirect but important threat to world peace and security;
2. Conduct significantly affecting more than one state;
3. Means or methods transcend national boundaries;
4. Cooperation of states is essential to enforce; and
5. Conduct potentially affecting citizens of more than one state.

However, criminologists including Allain and Jones (1997), Cho (2000), Caron, (2002), Bordin, (2014) and Greene (2019) have all been critical of the fact that the ILC even leaves open the possibility that there are other crimes against the peace and security of mankind than those appearing in the Draft Code, with Allain and Jones (1997) stating:

To adopt an approach whereby every offence is premised on a threat to peace and security, as opposed to an approach which simply treats the title ‘*code of crimes against the peace and security of mankind*’ as a general chapeau for all crimes under international law, runs certain risks.

The authors further comment that the ILC should have taken The Council of Europe’s convention on the protection of the environment through criminal law of 1998 as a guideline, not the crime of war, with a final reflection from Cho (2000) to the effect that:

A truly effective international environmental system will need to be modelled on similar sorts of devices. In other words, the human rights law should be a possible model for international environmental criminal law that deals with harms or threatened harms that significantly affect the ecological balance so as to deny the possibility of self-purification

The consistent failures in seriously considering ecocide as a crime, prompted the late Scottish lawyer Polly Higgins to launch a campaign in 2010 to make ecocide recognized as a ‘*crime against peace*.’ During the course of her advocacy, Higgins published two books on the subject, *Eradicating Ecocide* and *Earth Is Our Business*.

The Ecocide Campaign, the brainchild of the late Polly Higgins, calls for ecocide to join the four existing ‘*crimes against peace*’, namely

1. Genocide,
2. War crimes,
3. Crimes of aggression (such as unprovoked war), and
4. Crimes against humanity.

In support of her campaign, Higgins proposes this legal definition of ecocide:

The extensive destruction, damage to or loss of ecosystem(s) of a given territory, whether by human agency or by other causes, to such an extent that peaceful enjoyment by the inhabitants of that territory has been severely diminished.

In April 2010, Polly Higgins introduced a proposal to the UN International Law Commission to amend the Rome Statute to include ‘*ecocide*’ as a fifth crime against peace. If the crime of ecocide is added to the Rome Statute, ecocide cases could be heard by the International Criminal Court (ICC).

Higgins' recommendations to prevent ecocide include efforts to amend all compromise treaties, laws, rules and regulations:

1. Replace with prohibition of all damaging and destructive practices, and
2. Include provisions to enable restoration of damaged territories to be prioritized over existing practices that are premised on financial penalty alone.

Perhaps in some respects, simultaneously pragmatic and radical, Higgins (2010; 2012) and Higgins et al. (2013) proposed law of ecocide aims at the protection of the planet now in order that it is in a sustainable and healthy condition for those who inherit it. The challenge is to find ways to implement such visions of justice and law by both looking back at past efforts and attempts, and looking towards future efforts.

In 2015, law professor Laurent Neyret together with a team of 16 international lawyers, submitted a report titled '*From ecocrimes to ecocide.*' to the French Minister of Justice Christiane Taubira. The report contained 35 proposals aiming to better penalize environmental criminality at both national and international levels, justified by the fact that:

Environmental crime ranks 4th in the world for international illicit activities after drug trafficking, counterfeiting and human trafficking. And yet, studies show that this crime is rarely prosecuted by national authorities.

Ecocide was defined in the report as:

An intentional act committed as part of a widespread or systematic action that harms the safety of the planet.

Neyret's draft proposal for international conventions to better sanctioning environmental consisted of two parts:

1. One intended to fight against common environmental crimes, qualified as ecocrimes, and
2. The second relating to extraordinary environmental crimes, in the order of ecocide.

In June 2015, the Citizens' Convention for Climate also contributed to efforts to criminalise ecocide concentrating on the notion of planetary boundaries (discussed by Rockström et al., 2009), and characterising ecocide as:

Any action that has caused serious ecological damage, by contributing to clear and substantial breach of the planetary boundaries, committed with full knowledge of the consequences that were going to result from the breach and that could not be overlooked.

In the same year (2015), '*The International Parliamentary Alliance for the Recognition of Ecocide*' was initiated by Marie Toussaint, a Green Member of the European Parliament. The alliance aims at constituting a network of elected representatives willing to work together towards the recognition of the crime of ecocide within the International Criminal Court, stating that:

Facing the destruction of ecosystems, climate change and the mass extinction of biodiversity, it is time to criminalise those who threaten the planet and our rights. We, parliamentarians from all over the planet, unite in an international alliance for the recognition of the crime of Ecocide.

As a result of renewed calls to criminalise ecocide, a team of lawyers led by Valérie Cabanès launched: '*End Ecocide on Earth - International justice for the environment,*' with an opening statement stipulating that:

1. Our objective is to propose amendments to the Rome Statute, which governs the International Criminal Court.
2. It concerns expanding the area of competence for this jurisdiction, including the liability of legal entities in ecocide incrimination and not limiting the characterization of the crime to the act's intentional nature.

In a 2015 UN-HRC intergovernmental working group, the following statement issued by the UN cannot escape attention:

Destruction of the natural environment and peoples livelihoods violates the human rights to health, to water, to enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment. It can lead to.....forced eviction by mega projects, or by severe pollution, climate change or other disasters.

With reference to direct or systemic violations by TNCs, the UN-HRC (2015) finally refers to the crime of ecocide, which is described as:

Ecocide is the extensive damage to, destruction of or loss of ecosystem(s) of a given territory to such an extent that peaceful enjoyment by the inhabitants of that territory has been or will be severely diminished, or when systemic death and extermination of species occur.

The UN-HCR recognises that to prohibit mass damage and destruction of the Earth and creates a legal duty of care for all inhabitants, including all living beings, the inclusion of ecocide in international law aims at establishing the duty of care to prevent, prohibit and pre-empt both human-caused and natural catastrophes. The statement reflects on the final acceptance of the UN system in accepting ecocide as an environmental crime, even if in theory alone.

In 2016, the Office of the ICC Prosecutor said that it would prioritize crimes for prosecution that had resulted in environmental destruction, exploitation of natural resources or illegal dispossession of land. From being shoved out of the Rome Statute's ambit, crimes against the environment now seemed to be a focus of the ICC. On September 15, 2016, the Office of the Prosecutor for the ICC published a Policy Paper on Case Selection and Prioritization. This policy paper set out priorities in the cases the Prosecutor would investigate and bring before the Court.

The study of Vervaele and van Uhm (2017) finds that although the international community has been very active in regulatory protection of the environment, it has consistently refused or objected to integrate the criminal enforcement dimension in its policy and legal circles. The authors further observe that the international community has only recently focused on the interlink between environmental crime and organized crime, and related corruption and money laundering, but has again '*failed in taking an evolutionary leap forward*' in recognizing '*ecocide*' as the missing fifth crime against peace or international core crime

Vervaele and van Uhm conclude that:

In order to protect the environment through criminal law there is a substantial need for a more ecocentric approach to streamline the regulatory and enforcement chain in the policy cycle.

The 2018 UN Report '*Gaps in international environmental law and environment-related instruments: towards a Global Pact for the Environment*' (UN.SG Report A/73/419) discusses how the existing environmental law regime is fragmented, piecemeal, unclear and reactive. It appears that the UN is in the habit of going back on decisions taken or not taken previously.

The 2018 UN Report now claims that:

With no single overarching legal framework or institution and largely voluntary and non-binding obligations, international environmental law cannot be used to prosecute ecocide.

However, apart from criticising itself for inaction over decades, the UN appears to forget that the ILC is one of its arms that has been denying legal rights to the natural environment throughout its history in lawmaking.

As underlined in the IPCC's Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Report (AR6, 2021), and 5 decades after the first warning bells of Stockholm 1972 and volumes that have been published about the systemic breakdown in global environmental governance, it is finally recognised and accepted that humanity may have reached a stage of no return. It is finally recognised that scientific evidence points to tipping points already crossed and more to come. Emission of greenhouse gases and the destruction of ecosystems at current rates is already producing catastrophic consequences for our common environment and it is accelerating, not slowing down, claims the report.

International lawyers, environmentalists and a growing number of world leaders have finally recognised that '*ecocide*,' the widespread destruction of the environment would serve as a '*moral red line*' for the planet. In the same as genocide was condemned by the civilized world and justified intervention in the affairs of sovereign states, now, a small but growing number of world leaders including Pope Francis and French President Emmanuel Macron have begun citing an offense they say poses a similar threat to humanity and remains beyond the reach of existing legal conventions: '*ecocide*', or widespread destruction of the environment, describing ecocide as:

Massive contamination of air, land and water, or any action capable of producing an ecological disaster.

The present Pope of the Catholic Church has proposed '*making it a sin for Catholics*' while it is in fact a crime against not only humanity but against all forms of life on the planet.

During the long battle of Higgins and others as to whether the crime of ecocide should be included in the Rome Statute governing the activities of the International Criminal Court, an Independent Expert Panel for the Legal Definition of Ecocide was set up, spending six months preparing a definition for ecocide, now accepted as:

Unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts.

The next and crucial step is now in the waiting room. However, consensus is that, as Trevor Bach of the Audubon Magazine reported in 2021, '*finally the movement to establish ecocide as an official international crime is building global momentum.*' Already the European Parliament and political leaders in numerous countries, including France, Belgium, Finland, Spain and Canada, have expressed varying levels of support for the idea. All signs indicate that its time has come, and green criminology will be part of legal frameworks before long.

However, it remains to be seen whether the Code of the ICC will be modified to include the crime of ecocide, or whether there will be hesitations, opposition, and delays for the next decades to come. Perhaps the proposition of an independent International Environmental Criminal Court (IECC) discussed by several scholars over the years, including Abrami (2010), Venkatasamy and White (2015), Lehmen (2015), Bruce (2017), SoIntsev (2019) and

Lam Ching Wang (2022). Judging from years of inaction and lack of goodwill from the UN and the ILC, in spite of the global call for action on ecocide, the proposition of an independent IECC may have to be revived for serious consideration.

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